

We are running this survey to evaluate the effectiveness of an online simulation on the Gastrointestinal Smooth Muscle Activity. Your participation in this survey is voluntary, there are no marks associated with participation and you are free to decline from participation or withdraw at any time. Please answer all questions to the best of your knowledge.

1. When did you go through the simulation?

Check all that apply.

- I didn't look at the simulation.
- More than one day before the practical.
- The day before the practical.
- Immediately before going to the practical.
- During the practical.
- After the practical.

2. How long did you spend in total going through the simulation?

Mark only one option.

- I didn't look at the simulation.
- Less than 10 minutes.
- Between 10 and 20 minutes.
- More than 20 minutes. Please specify:

3. How many of the percentage change tables in the simulation did you fill in before the practical?

Mark only one option.

- None
- Some
- Most
- All

4. Please indicate on the scale (1: Strongly disagree to 5: Strongly agree) how you feel about the following statements.

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
	1	2	3	4	5
The simulation helped me understand the aims of the practical.	<input type="radio"/>				
I would have used the simulation to prepare for the practical even if it was an optional (rather than mandatory) activity.	<input type="radio"/>				

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
	1	2	3	4	5
The simulation didn't teach me anything about autonomic nerve regulation of gastrointestinal smooth muscle.	<input type="radio"/>				
The simulation helped me understand the concepts of autonomic nerve regulation of gastrointestinal smooth muscle function.	<input type="radio"/>				
I will probably come back to the simulation to study for exams.	<input type="radio"/>				
The simulation made it relatively straightforward to come up with the experimental design for the practical.	<input type="radio"/>				
I learnt less about gastrointestinal physiology from this practical than if I had been given step-by-step instructions of what to do.	<input type="radio"/>				
Completing the practical was not necessary for understanding the subject content, I could have done with just the simulation.	<input type="radio"/>				
Designing our own experiments for the practical was more engaging than following step-by-step instructions.	<input type="radio"/>				
I could have come up with a good experimental design for the practical without going through the simulation at all.	<input type="radio"/>				
Both the simulation and the practical were necessary to really understand autonomic control of gut motility.	<input type="radio"/>				
I would learn more from the simulation if it was an in-class activity.	<input type="radio"/>				
The simulation helped me prepare for the practical activity.	<input type="radio"/>				
Using the simulation during the practical helped me to get the experimental design right.	<input type="radio"/>				

5. Which aspect of the simulation did you find most useful?

Check all that apply.

- The text
- The data collection

- Filling in the tables
- The interpretation interactive animation
- The videos of the experimental setup and data recording
- Other (please specify) _____

6. Which aspect of the simulation has the most need for improvement?

Check all that apply.

- The text
- The data collection
- Filling in the tables
- The interpretation interactive animation
- The videos of the experimental setup and data recording
- Other (please specify) _____

7. Please write three words that you would use to describe the simulations:

8. Please tell us about any technical problems you may have encountered with the simulations:

9. How do you think the simulation could be improved to better convey the material of the practical class?
